

Investigating the Relationship between the Dark Web, Social Media and Online Radicalisation.

Evelina Pabricaite

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Address: London Metropolitan University, 166-220 Holloway Road, London, N7 8DB.

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Abstract

The internet plays a key role in radicalisation by connecting like-minded individuals, spreading extremist ideologies, and enabling online recruitment and incitement to real-world violence. This dissertation critically examines the shift of radicalisation from physical to digital spaces, emphasising importance of the social media, the dark web, and algorithmic amplification of extremist content. It explores the psychological models, sociological factors, emotional and behavioural patterns, that make individuals vulnerable in online environments. The study also evaluates UK de-radicalisation initiatives, particularly Prevent and Channel, noting their strengths in early intervention but highlighting their limitations in addressing the complex nature of online radicalisation.

Online radicalisation is identified as a multifaceted problem shaped by psychological, social, and political factors, as well as the decentralised and obscure structure of digital platforms. These dynamics complicate regulation and the detection of extremist content, particularly on platforms valuing anonymity or operating outside traditional oversight.

This literature-based study highlights the interplay between online and offline radicalisation, the challenges of current counter-extremism strategies, and the urgent need for more nuanced, interdisciplinary approaches to prevention and intervention.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Personal interest in cybercrime and terrorism comes from a fascination with how rapidly our world is changing, especially through technology, and how crime is evolving just as quickly to exploit it, especially how terrorists evolve to spread their ideas through all possible channels they can get access to. The digital age has brought incredible opportunities, but it has also opened doors to new and complex forms of criminal behaviour. Among these, cyberbullying and the rise of online radicalisation stands out as one of the most alarming and under-explored threats.

Research into online radicalisation in social media and especially in the dark web faces major challenges, including limited access to reliable data, small or context-specific samples, and difficulties in measuring impact or identifying causal factors. Variations in methods and definitions further hinder cross-study comparisons and generalisations.

1.2 Aim of the Study

This dissertation aims to explore the multifaceted role of the dark web and social media in online radicalisation, briefly mentioning the latest trends, such as the role of AI, video games and encrypted messaging apps. It seeks to provide analysis on how these digital platforms work, how they are utilised by extremist groups to propagate their ideologies, recruit new members and coordinate activities. By examining the psychological and sociological factors that contribute to individual susceptibility to extremist ideologies in online environments, the research intends to offer insights into the complex dynamics of online radicalisation. Ultimately, this study is a literature-based and contributes to the existing body of knowledge by synthesising findings from a wide range of secondary sources, including academic journals, books, policy documents, government reports, and case studies.

1.3 Research Objectives

The primary aim of this research is to investigate the role of the dark web and social media in online radicalisation. This central aim will be achieved by answering the following research questions:

1. How does the dark web and social media contribute to the process of online radicalisation?

2. What psychological and sociological factors increase individual susceptibility to extremist ideologies in online environments?

1.4 Methodology and Ethics

This study was conducted as desk-based research, drawing upon four main literature sources (Whittaker, 2022; Weimann, 2016; Bamsey and Montasari, 2023; Binder and Kenyon, 2022) with additional sources identified on the reference list. Targeted keyword searches were done using Google Scholar or Google, JSTOR. Literature searches were conducted between November and May 2024-25. There is an expanding body of both qualitative and quantitative studies exploring various factors relevant to online radicalisation.

The research on radicalisation online can cause potential risk of online harassment by terrorists, data breach and individual threats. Due to the sensitive nature of the topic, following The British Psychological Society (BPS) and the British Society of Criminology (BSC) ethical guidelines, there was no interaction with extremist content, individuals or groups, and no access to private or encrypted platforms due to the possible data breach and individual threats. All materials analysed were obtained from publicly available sources and care has been taken to avoid the uncritical reproduction or amplification of extremist narratives. The study fully complies with academic ethical guidelines, ensuring that all sources are properly cited and that discussions of radical content are handled with caution and academic responsibility.

1.5 Structure of the Dissertation

The first chapter explains what radicalisation is, traces the evolution of online radicalisation, showing how social media, the dark web, encrypted apps, and even video games have shifted radicalisation from organised physical spaces to decentralised online networks. It highlights the roles of anonymity, filter bubbles, algorithms and AI in amplifying extremist content, while noting the limitations due to restricted access to data from hidden online platforms.

The second chapter explores the psychological and sociological roots of radicalisation, using General Strain Theory and Social Identity Theory to explain how personal grievances and identity struggles make individuals vulnerable online and how disinformation can shape your beliefs, especially in a very young age. Chapter analyses how ISIS uses internet to recruit members and plan their attacks.

The third chapter further evaluates UK de-radicalisation efforts, particularly the Prevent and Channel programmes, it recognises their strengths in early intervention and multi-agency collaboration, but also points out conceptual vagueness, limited long-term tracking, and the need for strategies to be better suited to the digital nature of modern radicalisation. Chapter also briefly analyses how governments and tech companies are trying to stop ISIS radicalisation and help people leave extremist groups through de-radicalisation programmes, specifically analysing the Aarhus de-radicalisation model.

Chapter 2: Evolution of Contemporary Understandings of Radicalisation

2.1 Introduction

This chapter provides detailed analysis of the interconnected nature of online and offline radicalisation, highlighting how extremist groups use digital tools, from mainstream platforms to the dark web and social media, to expand their influence. It also explores the role of AI-driven propaganda, and the difficulties law enforcement faces in countering online radicalisation. However, studying this area is limited by challenges such as restricted access to primary data, the fast-changing nature of online platforms, and ethical concerns around surveillance and privacy. Furthermore, the disagreement among researchers regarding the internet's role in radicalisation makes it difficult to develop effective counterstrategies.

2.2 The Evolution of Online Radicalisation and Decentralised Terrorism

The nature of terrorism has shifted significantly since 9/11 (Hoffman, 2021). The days of centralised command structures like al-Qaeda are gone, today's threat comes from a multitude of decentralised, "homegrown" groups inspired by extremist ideologies. These scattered cells operate independently, mimicking their predecessors through online connections and self-directed planning. This virtual yet dangerous social movement thrives in internet chat rooms where individuals find inspiration, guidance, and a sense of belonging (Sageman, 2011). Use of the internet as a tool for communication and coordination emerged organically rather than through centralised planning. It coincided with the growth of internet access and increased surveillance of traditional physical meeting spaces, such as mosques, by local authorities. The restrictive environment limited opportunities for like-minded individuals to gather in person, prompting them to turn to online forums to exchange ideas, share information, and discuss their visions for the future. This shift began to take shape around 2004 (Sageman, 2011).

Only about 6% of the population in the Middle East has access to a computer, yet young people frequently gather in internet cafés to surf the web and connect with one another. Recognising the potential threat posed by this new form of communication, governments in the region actively monitor activities in these cafés. Despite this surveillance, young people often find ways to bypass scrutiny and

maintain their interactions. Similarly, in Indonesia, where internet usage is also low, members of terrorist networks rely on shared laptops or public computers at cafés to connect online (Sageman, 2011).

2.3 Defining Radicalisation

Numerous authors have proposed definitions of radicalisation. Functionally, radicalisation is defined as an increased readiness for intergroup conflict and a heightened commitment to it. Descriptively, it refers to a shift in beliefs, emotions, and behaviours that legitimise intergroup violence and the willingness to make sacrifices to defend one's group (Trip *et al.*, 2019). Radicalisation has historically been driven by social interactions in settings such as places of worship, religious schools, prisons, and meeting venues. Today, however, this process increasingly takes place on the Internet, where radicalising content can be disseminated effortlessly, reaching potential individuals more quickly, broadly, and on an unprecedented scale (Fernandez, Gonzalez-Pardo and Alani, 2019).

The concept of online radicalisation only gained prominence in policy and research circles in the late 2000's. Before this, the focus was on identifying the root causes of terrorism, examining societal conditions or individual factors that could lead to violence. The term radicalisation itself became widely used after the 2005 London bombings (Whittaker, 2022). Earlier studies explored how terrorists used the internet, but the shift toward analysing radicalisation as a process changed the approach. This new perspective framed online activity as a potential cause of radicalisation, creating a problem to be studied and addressed. In recent years, there has been an increase in research that examined the internet's role in influencing individuals, sometimes even considering it a key factor in (Whittaker, 2022).

Online radicalisation refers to the process through which individuals are exposed to, adopt, and internalise extremist beliefs and attitudes via the internet, particularly through social media and the dark web (Binder and Kenyon, 2022). Social media and the dark web are at the centre of this challenge, with studies indicating that much of online radicalisation begins on these platforms (Vaughan Williams, 2024).

2.4 The Interconnectedness Between Online and Offline Radicalisation

Policymakers have repeatedly identified online radicalisation as a major security threat. Key European institutions, including the Council of Europe, the European Commission, and Europol, have emphasised

its growing risks. In 2017, French President Emmanuel Macron and former UK Prime Minister Theresa May launched the “French-British Action Plan” to combat online extremism. Similarly, the U.S. government, the FBI, and the United Nations have also recognised the urgent need to address this issue (Whittaker, 2022).

The internet has increasingly replaced traditional spaces like mosques and community centres as key hubs for extremist recruitment. Online platforms such as the Hizba, Faluja, and Ikhlas forums function similarly to social networking sites like Facebook, offering interactive spaces where users can share videos, engage in discussions, and form virtual communities (Hearne and Laiq, 2019). By early 2019, global internet usage had reached 57%, with 4.4 billion users, while mobile social media usage covered 42%, or 3.2 billion people. This has allowed individuals to share ideas, communicate, and interact more quickly than ever, even with audiences on the other side of the globe (Schmid, 2020). The information revolution has enabled terrorist groups to shift from traditional warfare tactics to a new form of conflict at the societal level. While such organisations have always conducted psychological operations, they now can conduct information operations on a much larger scale. Recognising the power of knowledge and influence, terrorists leverage social media and the internet for brand management and propaganda to sway public opinion and recruit new members. Whereas they once relied on traditional media like TV, radio, and print, the internet allows them to amplify and diversify their messages, even with localised approaches by individual cells. As a result, terrorist groups now have greater control over the flow of information, placing more focus on information operations (Schmid, 2020).

While many radicalised individuals utilise the internet to some extent, radicalisation is rarely attributed solely to online influences. Increasingly, it is recognised that online and offline factors are interconnected, often reinforcing one another. However, both passive and active exposure to extremist content online, along with interactions with others who share violent extremist views, are linked to the development of extremist attitudes and behaviours. Additionally, a substantial proportion of violent extremist offenders, up to 60%, either undergo radicalisation primarily through online means or are significantly influenced by online interactions during the process (Wolbers *et al.*, 2023). While there are a few cases of “lone wolves” where the internet appears to have been the primary driver of radicalisation, most cases suggest that real world, face-to-face interactions play a more decisive role. However, the internet fosters an imagined radical community for some users, reinforcing the concept of the Ummah (the global Islamic community) frequently referenced in jihadist propaganda. For certain individuals, this virtual world takes on a sense of reality beyond the online sphere (Schmid, 2013).

With terrorist activities increasingly shifting online, cases without a digital footprint have become rare. Scholars debate the internet's exact influence on radicalisation with some arguing that repeated exposure to extremist content actively encourages violent action, while others see it as merely accelerating an existing process. However, findings remain mixed on how deeply online and offline radicalisation is interconnected (Valentini, Lorusso and Stephan, 2020). A major challenge in studying this phenomenon is the lack of primary data, making it difficult to establish concrete evidence on how online radicalisation translates into offline violence. Additionally, there is a need to bridge the gap between digital and real-world perspectives, as treating them separately can lead to ineffective countermeasures (Valentini, Lorusso and Stephan, 2020). The connection between online radicalisation and real-world violence continues to be a critical policy and research issue (Aryaeinejad and Scherer, 2024). The sheer volume of online content, spanning multiple languages and levels of encryption, makes the task of combating terrorist propaganda immensely complex (Schmid, 2013)

2.5 Waves of Radicalisation

The first wave of online radicalisation began in 1984 with the rise of bulletin board systems created by far-right extremists. Networks like the Beam's Aryan Liberty Net allowed activists to connect, share propaganda, and bypass legal restrictions on spreading hate. These early platforms provided a space for extremist ideologies to grow, reaching younger audiences and fostering discussions about violent action. While it's unclear if they directly inspired attacks, they laid the foundation for online radicalisation. By the mid-1990s, these bulletin boards evolved into permanent websites like Stormfront, solidifying the internet as a powerful tool for extremist recruitment and coordination (Ware, 2023).

The second wave of online radicalisation emerged in the mid-2000s with the rise of major social media platforms like Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), YouTube, and Instagram. Unlike earlier, niche forums that required specific access, these public platforms allowed extremists to spread their ideology widely, reaching friends, family, and global networks. Search engines made extremist content easier to find, while social media revolutionised activism, playing a key role in events like the Arab Spring. However, the same tools that enabled activism also allowed extremist groups to exploit political instability, using social media and dark web to expand their influence and recruit followers (Ware, 2023).

The third wave of online radicalisation is both an evolution and a shift from its predecessor. Extremist organisations and ideologies play a lesser role, while lone actors now function as their own propagandists, sharing manifestos and livestreams. The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated mass

radicalisation, often fuelled by conspiracy theories and misinformation, especially using online platforms. Unlike earlier social media movements, this generation prioritises anonymity and encrypted platforms like Telegram and Gab, making monitoring and intervention more difficult. Extremists use fast-moving, ephemeral discussions on sites like '4chan', reinforcing their views in closed online ecosystems that increase the risk of radicalisation and violence (Ware, 2023).

2.6 The Role of the Dark Web

The Dark Web, also referred to as the Darknet, is a hidden segment of the internet that is part of the larger deep web (Finklea, 2017). Unlike the surface web, which is accessible through standard search engines like Google or Bing, the Dark Web requires specialised tools and configurations, such as the TOR (The Onion Router) network, for access. It is characterised by elevated levels of user anonymity, encrypted communication, concealed IP addresses, and untraceable data exchanges. These features make it distinct from other parts of the web (Raman et al., 2023). Originally developed for secure military communications and to support freedom of speech, the Dark Web now serves both legitimate and illicit purposes (Warf, 2018).

While it provides a safe space for whistleblowers, journalists, and activists operating in repressive environments, it is also widely associated with illegal activities. These include human trafficking, child exploitation, drug and weapon sales, financial fraud, and the promotion of terrorism (Raman et al., 2023). Cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin are frequently used within the Dark Web, as they enable untraceable financial transactions, further bolstering its anonymous nature (Awasthi, 2024). The Dark Web operates as a complex ecosystem with multiple roles. It functions as an e-commerce marketplace for both legal and illegal goods, a communication platform for secure exchanges, a hub for enabling cybercrime, a medium for untraceable financial transactions, and a source of valuable threat intelligence. These diverse roles make it a focal point for cybersecurity research and law enforcement efforts (Adel and Norouzifard, 2024).

Since the late 1990s, terrorists have used various online platforms to share propaganda, recruit members, and coordinate activities. However, the Surface Web's lack of anonymity led terrorists to shift to the Dark Web, where decentralised, anonymous networks help evade detection and bypass counter-terrorism efforts to shut down extremist platforms (Weimann, 2016). Dark Web serves as a platform that enables individuals to progress through various stages of radicalisation. The process often begins with being 'susceptible' to extremist ideas and encountering a 'radicaliser' through forums, chat rooms, or encrypted platforms. This initial contact may lead to exposure to ideological content, new

behavioural patterns, and engagement with exclusive online communities. Over time, individuals may isolate themselves from traditional social connections, narrowing their circle to those who reinforce radical beliefs. This progression culminates in a 'hardening phase,' characterised by consuming violent propaganda, including graphic videos of terrorist activities, executions, and battle footage, which are easily accessible on the Dark Web (Veldhuis and Staun, 2009). Regulating radicalisation at the Dark Web remains a significant challenge due to its decentralised and encrypted infrastructure. Research in this area has increasingly turned to advanced technologies such as machine learning and artificial intelligence to monitor Dark Web activity, detect criminal enterprises such as terrorism, and improve cyber threat intelligence. Despite these advancements, the complexity of enforcing comprehensive policies highlights the need for continued innovation in both detection and prevention strategies (Raman et al., 2023).

2.7 Social Media and Power of Algorithms

Social media has become a platform where a wide range of information is shared, not just in everyday life, but also during events like shootings and terror attacks (Riebe *et al.*, 2018). Social media has proven particularly effective for spreading propaganda and recruiting for several reasons: it allows terrorists to reach a much broader audience than traditional media, which previously required direct personal contact for spreading radicalising messages, materials, and ideological grooming (BPC, 2018). Social media searches revealed higher online activity among far-right extremists, with Facebook being the most used platform (Aryaeinejad and Scherer, 2024). Today, platforms like X, Instagram, Facebook, and YouTube enable terrorists to instantly share their messages with users across the globe, often using compelling images or videos (BPC, 2018). The modern social media radicalisation model thrives on a culture of provocative and inflammatory content, where users continuously post increasingly extreme material (Ware, 2023). Unlike traditional websites, these social media services are free, user-friendly, and can be often used anonymously (BPC, 2018). Social media became a place where individuals and groups can engage in discussions with minimal oversight from authorities, allowing radical messages to reach global audiences. In recent years, there have been growing calls to allocate resources to monitor and curb the spread of radical content on social media (Rosner, 2019).

The spread of information often is influenced more by the number of likes and comments than the credibility of the source, leading to the amplification of emotional content. Social media fills users with information that aligns with their pre-existing beliefs, which can contribute to group polarisation and, in some cases, radicalisation. Additionally, the anonymity offered by social media allows for less

constrained expression, which can lead to verbal attacks and the spread of extreme ideas (Riebe *et al.*, 2018).

One of the reasons why social media is so effective for terrorists to radicalise is the power of platform algorithms, which connect users to content that aligns with their existing preferences. Social media giants rely on selling attention, making their profits dependent on attracting users' attention. These platforms collect detailed personal information about users and use algorithms to analyse this data to show content that keeps users engaged (BPC, 2018). For example, Facebook personalises users' news feeds based on past interactions, while Google and YouTube sort search results and video recommendations based on a user's location and previous activity. This creates "filter bubbles" where users being shown content that confirms their beliefs, making it harder for them to encounter opposing viewpoints. As platforms gather more data, their algorithms become increasingly effective at anticipating user preferences, leading to more radical or extreme content recommendations over time (BPC, 2018). While free speech is a protected right, platforms like Facebook prohibit hate speech under their community guidelines. The lack of clear global definitions for extremism and terrorism creates challenges in balancing privacy and security online. Extremist groups exploit the internet's reach to spread harmful content and radicalise users, often outpacing the ability of moderators and governments to respond effectively (Bamsey and Montasari, 2023). As the internet becomes more embedded in daily life, the role of social media in terrorism, violent extremism, and radicalisation remains a sincere concern (Aryaeinejad and Scherer, 2024).

2.8 Messaging Apps, Video Games and AI as a Driving Tool for Propaganda

Terrorist groups and radicalised individuals increasingly rely on encrypted communication platforms like Telegram, Signal, and Discord. Telegram has become a primary hub for extremist networks due to its strong encryption and anonymity features. With eight hundred million users, it remains the platform of choice for clandestine communications, allowing terrorist groups to operate beyond the reach of authorities (UNCCT, 2024). Signal has also gained traction, with a 677% surge in downloads in early 2023, providing an additional layer of security for extremists seeking private communication channels. Discord, initially popular among gaming communities, has been exploited by radical groups for propaganda dissemination, recruitment, and operational planning. Its file-sharing features, voice and video chat, and integrations with third-party apps create vulnerabilities that extremists exploit. Reports indicate that radical groups use Discord to spread extremist content and distribute harmful materials, often using AI-generated voices and videos (UNCCT, 2024). Terrorist groups are increasingly exploring

AI. For example, ISIS propagandist Bahrun Naim used a bot to send automated messages and share bomb-making guides in Bahasa, Indonesia (Zeiger and Gyte, 2019). Al-Shabaab's news agency, Shahada, used a Telegram bot to stay connected with followers despite bans. Though there is no confirmed use of tools like GPT-2 by terrorists yet, experts warn AI could soon be used to spread extremist content and manipulate online discourse, challenging current detection systems that struggle to distinguish AI from human-generated material (Zeiger and Gyte, 2019).

The use of video games in extremist activities is not a new phenomenon, with groups having created and repurposed games for over two decades. Some experts argue that gaming platforms, with their strong social networking features, can be exploited to target and influence a young, vulnerable audience. While extremist groups rarely create their own games with the intent to recruit, such games are often used to reinforce ideological beliefs and encourage individuals already involved in extremist movements to commit violence (Whittaker, 2022). However, the broader concern lies in the use of gaming-related platforms for extremist activity. Several online platforms, including Steam, Discord, Twitch, and DLive, have been found to host right-wing extremist content, including support for terrorist organisations. Although there is no clear evidence of a coordinated strategy to recruit new members through gaming, these spaces often serve as gathering points for already radicalised individuals (Whittaker, 2022).

Chapter 3: Social and Psychological Factors of Radicalisation

3.1 Introduction

This chapter looks at the different ways people become radicalised and questions the idea that extreme beliefs always lead to violence. It covers key theories like General Strain Theory, which links personal struggles and frustrations to extremist actions, and Social Identity Theory, which explains how feeling excluded or seeking belonging can push people toward radical groups. The chapter uses ISIS as an example of how online tools can make radicalisation more effective and far-reaching.

3.2 Explaining Online Radicalisation Through Traditional Theories

Focusing on radicalisation alone can mistakenly suggest that radical beliefs are a necessary precursor to terrorism. Most people with radical ideas do not engage in violence, and many terrorists, even those claiming a cause, may not be deeply ideological. Different individuals follow varied pathways to terrorism, influenced by several factors over time and in different contexts. While adopting extremist beliefs is one potential path to violent extremism, it is not the only one (Borum, 2011). Since the late 1960's, academic researchers have sought to understand the causes of terrorism by examining it across various levels: Socio-cultural context, behavioural context, group, network, organisation contexts. Early studies primarily focused on the individual level if the extreme behaviours associated with terrorism were indicative of mental or personality abnormalities (Borum, 2011).

3.3 Strain Theory

One of the most promising frameworks for understanding radicalisation and violent extremism is the General Strain Theory (GST), developed by Robert Agnew (Skoczyliis and Andrews, 2022). It explains criminal behaviour in relation to negative life experiences. Agnew expands on Merton's Strain Theory, and he argues that strain arises from blocked goals, loss of positive experiences, or exposure to harmful situations, leading to stress. This stress, combined with a desire to avoid further strain or achieve social goals, can drive individuals to commit crimes (Skoczyliis and Andrews, 2022). This is more likely when there are few legal ways to address the strain and limited social controls over one's actions. Agnew also argues that strain tends to build over time. The more strain a person experiences, the greater the likelihood they will turn to illegal methods, such as crime, to cope with the situation. Since the

introduction of GST, it has been used to explain various forms of criminal behaviour, including extremism and radicalisation (Skoczylis and Andrews, 2022). Strain theory provides a lens through which terrorism and radicalisation can be viewed as responses to personal and collective strains, often stemming from anger, humiliation, hopelessness, and perceived grievances (Cherney *et al.*, 2022). Few studies have explored the role of strain in the development of extremist attitudes. The idea that the inability to achieve certain societal goals, such as those related to masculinity, might lead to criminal behaviour, aligns with the observation that various forms of extremism exhibit hyper-masculine characteristics, especially in the context of violent extremism. However, this perspective often overlooks the involvement of women in extremism, both violent and non-violent (Skoczylis and Andrews, 2022). Increasingly, research has shown that women play significant roles within extremist groups, including in leadership, propaganda, and recruitment, indicating that more attention is required to explore gendered pathways to extremism. Moreover, strain experienced collectively can contribute to political violence, and various scholars have argued that this strain can play a causal role in terrorism (Skoczylis and Andrews, 2022). Strains experienced during childhood are considered influential in the development of criminal behaviour. The literature on extremism suggests that youth can be especially vulnerable to radicalisation (Skoczylis and Andrews, 2022). Additionally, factors commonly explored in risk assessments, such as the search for personal significance, prior behaviour, mental health issues, substance abuse, and extremist peers, closely align with the factors considered strain in GST. This overlap suggests that GST holds promise as a criminological framework that can help bridge the gap between the study of extremism and radicalisation (Skoczylis and Andrews, 2022).

3.4 Social Identity Theory

Human beings are inherently social creatures. Through our social connections, we learn about what is right and wrong, true and false, what is acceptable and what lies beyond the pale (Strindberg, 2020). These connections enable us to forge friendships, cultivate loyalties, express solidarity, and experience empathy, while also fostering rivalries, grievances, and conflict. Our social relationships not only help us share experiences and exchange opinions but also shape our worldviews, guide our personal narratives, and transform individual aspirations into collective goals. In this way, social ties can both promote unity and, conversely, accentuate divisions between those who belong to our group and those who do not. Social Identity Theory (SIT) delves into how social identity emerges, evolves, and influences group dynamics (Strindberg, 2020). It examines the processes behind the formation of groups, the development of their worldviews, and the evolution of their narratives. SIT allows us to explore how individuals within a group view themselves in relation to others, and it highlights the significance of understanding a group's identity to identify what truly matters to its members. The manipulation of

social identity and the narratives associated with it can play a significant role in the radicalisation process, as it is often within these identity frameworks that extreme ideologies take root (Strindberg, 2020). SIT can help us to understand the experiences of European Muslims, particularly in terms of how religious identity and social integration influence the likelihood of adopting extremist ideologies (Al Raffie, 2013).

When individuals have a weak commitment to their religious identity, they may struggle to fit into mainstream social groups and lack alternative sources of identity, becoming suitable for radicalisation (Al Raffie, 2013). Conversely, individuals with a strong religious identity may also become susceptible to extremism if they experience discrimination. In such cases, discrimination can reinforce their religious commitment while deepening their sense of alienation from society. Extremist groups can then appeal to this sense of exclusion by offering community, recognition, and a clear identity (Al Raffie, 2013).

SIT suggests that people who are well integrated into society, are less likely to be drawn to extremism. In more secular societies, where religion plays a smaller role, individuals may define themselves through other affiliations, such as nationality or profession, which can serve as protective factors against radicalisation (Al Raffie, 2013).

3.5 Psychological/Sociological Factors on Radicalisation Online

The psychological and sociological reasoning behind radicalisation often involves a combination of perceived grievances, identity struggles, and cognitive biases, which make individuals more susceptible to extremist ideologies and beliefs (Trip *et al.*, 2019). Various psychological models have been proposed to explain the process of radicalisation. Borum in 2003 introduced a four-stage radicalisation model to explain terrorist's mindset (King and Taylor, 2011). First stage starts from context, where individuals perceive an issue (e.g., poverty or restrictions) as "not right". It follows with comparison, where the issue is framed as unjust. Attribution, where blame can be assigned to a specific target and lastly, a reaction, where the responsible party is being demonised, justifying aggression. The second and third stages involve indoctrination, while the fourth aligns with extremism and radicalisation (Borum, 2004).

Moghaddam's staircase model (2005) describes radicalisation as a step-by-step process (Fernandez, Gonzalez-Pardo & Alani, 2019). It starts with perceived deprivation - feelings of injustice and hardship. When attempts to resolve these issues fail, frustration builds and redirects as anger toward a perceived enemy. This can lead to moral engagement, where individuals begin to sympathise with extremist

ideologies that oppose this enemy. Some of these sympathisers then join extremist groups, supporting their violence and seeing it as justified. In the final stage, a few go on to commit terrorist acts, having mentally accepted violence as necessary. However, critics argue the model is too linear and does not reflect the complex, and varied pathways to terrorism (Fernandez, Gonzalez-Pardo and Alani, 2019). People with marginalised or unconventional views, such as antisocial beliefs or conspiracy theories, often feel excluded in their offline lives and seek connection and validation online. This sense of loneliness has been linked to risky online behaviour, including a higher likelihood of radicalisation and dark web use (Sirola, Savolainen & Oksanen, 2024). Many dark web users exhibit weak offline social ties and are typically highly active, tech-savvy individuals with problematic online engagement. Their use of mainstream platforms can serve as a gateway to the dark web, where unregulated environments enable the formation of communities centred on deviant or extremist interests (Sirola, Savolainen & Oksanen, 2024).

Radicalisation is driven by a mix of personal, social, and political factors. These include life's uncertainties, identity struggles, feelings of alienation, integration difficulties, and political grievances often tied to moral outrage or a desire for revenge. A key factor is the human need for significance - belonging, respect, achievement, and self-worth. Extremist groups exploit this by using positive emotions like pride, love, power, and belonging to attract and retain followers (Shafieiou & Haq, 2023). Online radicalisation often involves retreating into selective digital spaces rather than fully cutting ties with the outside world (Torok, 2013). These spaces, such as extremist forums, encrypted chats, and propaganda sites, act like self-imposed "institutions." Unlike traditional institutions, such as prisons, that physically isolate people, these digital environments isolate users mentally and ideologically. People voluntarily immerse themselves, becoming shielded from alternative views, which reinforces extremist beliefs and accelerates radicalisation (Torok, 2013). Several studies show that most people, exposed to extremist content, do not become violent, but those who do, often share common, so called, risk factors. These include being young, male, unemployed, mentally unwell, having low self-control, personal grievances, or criminal backgrounds. While exposure alone is not enough to cause radicalisation, it can speed up the process in already at-risk individuals (Wolbers et al., 2023). Disinformation and fake news on social media further complicate this issue. They distort public understanding, particularly among youth aged 15–24, by shaping political views and behaviours (Akram & Nasar, 2023).

3.6 Case Study of ISIS Radicalisation

Since June 2014, the world has faced a new and alarming terrorist threat in the form of the Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS). The escalation of terrorist attacks in Europe between 2016 and 2017, attributed to ISIS, has brought terrorism to the forefront of global concerns. This is understandable, given that ISIS has successfully recruited tens of thousands of fighters from across the world. Considering this widespread appeal, policymakers, intelligence agencies, and governments have been working to understand the factors that drive individuals to join ISIS, especially as the group has expanded its influence into the online space, using the dark web and social media to radicalise and recruit globally (Tolis, 2019).

ISIL, also known as ISIS, is a violent terrorist group responsible for causing immense suffering in Syria and Iraq through the promotion of an Islamist extremist ideology. They are a brutal organisation that seeks to impose its rule through violence and extortion. ISIL's claim of establishing an 'Islamic State' or 'caliphate' lacks any legitimate theological foundation (Home Office, 2015). ISIL's propaganda is crafted to present the group as a compelling alternative to life in the west, particularly targeting young people, now mostly moving on the internet. It portrays ISIL as the powerful creators of a new Islamic state, where all Muslims, both men and women, have a duty to join. The propaganda sources ignore the reality that ISIL is a terrorist organisation responsible for the deaths of innocent men, women, and children. When ISIL releases propaganda online, it encourages supporters to share the material widely on social media, amplifying its reach (Home Office, 2015). ISIL uses four main propaganda themes to attract and recruit people, often leveraging these narratives in social media discussions. First, they promote an image of success, claiming to be the "winning side" and offering an exciting and purposeful life. Their slogan "Baqiyah wa-Tatamaddad" (remaining and expanding), emphasises their victories, despite the reality that ISIL faces widespread opposition in Syria and Iraq. Second, ISIL depicts their so-called "Caliphate" as a utopian state where Muslims will find status, belonging, and purpose. They assert it is the duty of Muslims in the west to migrate there, claiming that all Sunni Muslims are welcome. In truth, this "Caliphate" has been rejected by most Islamic scholars globally, and ISIL's well-documented abuses, such as the exploitation of women and children and the killing of civilians, contradict their claims (Home Office, 2015). Third, ISIL propaganda falsely insists it is the personal duty of Muslims to support them and travel to the "Caliphate." Islamic scholars have universally dismissed this notion, affirming that no such obligation exists. Finally, ISIL portrays itself as the only protector of Sunni Muslims against threats from the Assad regime, the Iraqi army, or the west. They emphasise their provision of food and services in Syria and Iraq, even though the reality is that most Sunnis fear and oppose ISIL, recognising them as a danger to their safety and lives (Home Office, 2015). In recent years,

there has been an increasing public awareness of how radical jihadist movements utilise social media to radicalise, recruit, and mobilise individuals (Whittaker, 2022). Extremist groups use the Internet's low cost, speed, and global reach to operate anonymously and across borders. They exploit interactive platforms to spread hate speech, recruit members, and radicalise individuals by isolating them from offline connections. The Internet also serves as a resource for tactical learning and planning attacks (Hassan *et al.*, 2018).

Groups like ISIS have used the dark web and communication apps for propaganda, recruitment, and coordination, distributing guides on privacy, weapon construction, and secure communication (Awasthi, 2024). After the November 2015 Paris attacks, ISIS intensified its use of the Dark Web to protect its supporters' identities and safeguard its propaganda materials. For example, ISIS's media outlet Al-Hayat Media Centre posted links on extremist forums directing users to its Dark Web site and Telegram channels (Weimann, 2016). Telegram, known for its encryption, has been a favoured platform for ISIS to distribute content and coordinate activities, offering tools like private messaging and secure links to Tor services. This shift highlights the growing use of anonymous online platforms by terrorist groups to evade surveillance and sustain their operations (Weimann, 2016). Following the Paris attacks, ISIS announced the migration of its Isdarat website to the Dark Web, providing a secure ".onion" address for its propaganda archives. This shift was a direct response to increased constraints on its Surface Web activities, with domains frequently being removed. Additionally, extremist groups have developed tools and resources to ensure online anonymity. For example, al-Qaeda's "al-Aqsa IT Team" released a manual titled "Tor Browser Security Guidelines," detailing steps for safely using the Tor browser and evading geolocation and detection by counter-terrorism agencies (Weimann, 2016).

The Islamist State (IS) is often regarded as one of the first terrorist organisations to effectively harness social media for spreading propaganda, raising funds, and radicalising and recruiting individuals worldwide. In 2015, a report by the U.S. Government revealed that IS had successfully recruited over 25,000 foreign fighters, including approximately 4,500 from Europe and North America (Fernandez, Gonzalez-Pardo and Alani, 2019).

ISIS's propaganda machine is more sophisticated than that of previous terrorist organisations, both in content and distribution. It operates through two key divisions: Al-Hayat Media, which focuses on recruitment and portraying an idealised society, and Mu'assassat al-Furqan, which spreads fear. Media operations play a crucial role within ISIS, with propaganda personnel often receiving higher status and pay than the fighters. The organisation employs former tech and news industry professionals skilled in video production and graphic design (Gerstel, 2016). ISIS has a far more advanced media operation

than Al-Qaeda and its affiliates, producing high-quality propaganda online with professional editing and cinematography. Unlike the low-resolution videos once used by Osama Bin Laden, ISIS creates Hollywood style, hour long films highlighting life in the so-called Caliphate and its military victories. Additionally, ISIS has produced original nasheeds (jihadi songs) that serve as background music in its propaganda videos (Gerstel, 2016).

Talking about X in particular, ISIS terrorists spread ideological messages designed to intimidate and instil fear. By posting religious declarations and concise statements, they maximise their reach and influence. Their use of X helps create a climate of fear while reinforcing their messaging, turning the platform into an echo chamber for their ideology (Awan, 2017). ISIS has often used X for posting graphic content, such as images of beheadings. In one instance, ISIS supporters used the hashtag #WorldCup alongside the message: "This is our ball...it has skin on it," to spread fear (Awan, 2017). X allows ISIS's media wing, Al-Furqan, to quickly disseminate messages and reinforce its narrative through reposts. ISIS has used X to provide real-time updates from fighters in Syria, aiming to attract young recruits and maintain global appeal. ISIS operates around 30 online media groups, such as Al-Battar Media Group, which translates and promotes ISIS content. The "Billion Muslims Campaign," launched on June 13, 2014, generated over 22,000 posts in four days, and the hashtag "#AllEyesOnISIS" accumulated over 30,000 posts. Although X has suspended many ISIS-linked accounts, the group continues to maintain an online presence (Awan, 2017).

It is important to mention, for individuals associated with ISIS, de-radicalisation programmes are very specific and typically involve a special combination of ideological rehabilitation, psychological counselling, and vocational training. Since ISIS ideology is rooted in an extreme interpretation of Islam, it is harder to de-radicalise ex-terrorists than to radicalise them through religion. Religious re-education is a crucial component, where scholars challenge the group's theological justifications for violence (Ghosh and Chan, 2017).

Experience shows that violent extremists often have a limited or distorted understanding of religion, shaped by extremist ideology. Chaplains are key in broadening their religious knowledge, promoting critical thinking, and challenging extremist views by exposing offenders to diverse theological sources and scholars. They also provide a safe space for offenders to express emotions, frustrations, and grievances, acting as trusted confidants. This support helps alleviate internal tensions and aids in the rehabilitation and disengagement process (CDPC, 2016).

Chapter 4: De-Radicalisation Programmes and Their Efficiency

4.1 Introduction

This chapter explores the concept, effectiveness, and challenges of de-radicalisation programmes, such as Prevent, Channel and The Aarhus de-radicalisation model, as part of broader counter-terrorism efforts. It examines how these initiatives aim to disengage individuals from extremist ideologies and prevent re-engagement in violence through various strategies, including education, mentorship, and psychological support. The chapter also discusses case studies, policy measures, and the impact of online regulations in combating radicalisation, highlighting both successes and limitations in different global contexts.

4.2 Defining De-Radicalisation

If radicalisation is a vague concept, the same applies to de-radicalisation. Experts in terrorism studies have noted a lack of clarity in how de-radicalisation is defined (Schmid, 2013). Often, the term is used too broadly to describe any effort to prevent radicalisation, rather than a distinct process focused specifically on reversing it. This misuse creates a logical contradiction, since the prefix “de-” implies the process begins after radicalisation has already occurred. Despite this, many programmes across different countries group a wide range of efforts, those aimed at preventing radicalisation, mitigating its progression, and intervening in active cases, under the single banner of "deradicalisation." This is misleading, it obscures the differences in strategy, focus, and intended outcomes, making it harder to design effective interventions and evaluate their success (Clutterbuck, 2015). Using the term "deradicalisation" often implies a singular, linear process, typically assumed to involve a change in beliefs that results in a change in behaviour. Radicalisation and de-radicalisation are complex and vary between individuals (Clutterbuck, 2015). The concept of de-radicalisation, particularly as a method to reverse radical beliefs, gained attention in the UK's counterterrorism strategy after 9/11. As people influenced by violent jihadist ideologies were arrested and imprisoned, authorities faced a new challenge: how to manage these individuals during incarceration and after their release, especially since many were not serving life sentences (Clutterbuck, 2015).

4.3 Online Radicalisation

On April 29, 2021, the EU adopted a regulation to combat the spread of terrorist content online. It grants member states the authority to issue removal orders requiring internet platforms to take down such content within one hour. These rules apply to all service providers operating in the EU, regardless of their location. Platforms must implement measures to prevent misuse while maintaining the freedom to choose their approach. The regulation covers content that incites terrorism, provides instructions for attacks, or recruits members, ensuring fundamental rights are respected and allowing appeals for removed content (European Council, 2022). In 2015, Europol established the EU Internet Referral Unit (EU IRU) to detect, investigate, counter terrorist and extremist content online, supporting member states in these efforts. That same year, the EU launched the Radicalisation Awareness Network (RAN), bringing together over 6,000 frontline practitioners, including teachers, police officers, and prison staff. RAN focuses on sharing best practices and improving understanding of radicalisation, helping to identify vulnerable individuals and develop effective prevention strategies (European Council, 2022).

In March 2019, Facebook, X, Microsoft, and YouTube were asked to provide details on their annual budgets for combating online extremism on their platforms. When these companies failed to provide the requested information, U.S. Government representatives issued a statement criticising the lack of transparency, stating that vague explanations and general safety measures were insufficient (Zeiger and Gyte, 2019). In the same year, the European Parliament passed a regulation titled "Tackling the dissemination of terrorist content online," following a resolution on April 17. The legislation aims to prevent the misuse of hosting services for terrorist activities and improve public security across European societies. It specifically addresses what social media platforms, or "hosting services," can do to regulate and remove terrorist content. Some of the more contentious provisions, such as requiring platforms to remove content within one hour of posting, were revised to allow more time for these companies to act (Zeiger and Gyte, 2019). However, legislation and policy efforts to prevent the spread of terrorist content online, face various challenges. Policymakers, often lacking expertise in communication technologies, may misunderstand how internet and social media companies operate, particularly smaller platforms like Telegram, Signal, and Reddit. As modern technologies like AI and decentralised web services (DWeb) emerge, governments struggle to stay informed and adapt their responses, complicating efforts to regulate and moderate content effectively. Close collaboration between governments and private companies is crucial, especially for lesser-known platforms, to tackle the evolving challenges of online extremism (Zeiger and Gyte, 2019).

4.4 De-Radicalisation Programmes

De-radicalisation programmes aim to help individuals leave extremist and terrorist groups as part of broader efforts to counter violent extremism. Programmes vary widely in structure, methods, and goals, as no single approach fits all cases (Hearne and Laiq, 2019). These interventions use mentoring, education, employment support, and psychological assistance, often involving partnerships between organisations and government bodies for an integrated approach (Marsden, 2019). De-radicalisation programmes operate at various levels, from government-led initiatives to NGO-supported efforts, and are tailored to specific contexts and target populations (Saha, 2024).

In the early 2000s, intervention programmes shifted toward changing the ideas and attitudes linked to extremism, with some of the earliest initiatives emerging in the Middle East and Southeast Asia. Today, de-radicalisation programmes play a crucial role in counter-terrorism efforts worldwide, addressing the ideological, social, and personal factors that lead individuals into extremism (Marsden, 2019). These programmes aim to protect the public, reduce the risk of reengagement in violence, and help individuals build positive futures. Targeting convicted terrorists or those deeply involved in extremism, de-radicalisation is considered a tertiary intervention, focusing on disengagement. This contrasts with primary interventions, which prevent radicalisation by addressing root causes, and secondary interventions, which support individuals at risk of extremism (Marsden, 2019). Quantitative data suggests that de-radicalisation programmes effectively reduce recidivism and terrorist activities globally. Saudi Arabia and Germany show the most significant declines, indicating that well-funded, comprehensive programmes yield substantial security benefits. Notably, Saudi Arabia's lower recidivism rate (5%) compared to Bangladesh (12%) underscores the impact of strong programme design and adequate funding (Saha, 2024). Evaluating radicalisation prevention programmes requires understanding the socio-political context in which they operate (Clutterbuck, 2015).

A survey by the Institute for Strategic Dialogue analysing thirteen de-radicalisation programmes found that voluntary participation is key to success, as personal commitment plays a crucial role. Trust between participants and programme staff is essential, and involving former extremists can be beneficial due to their credibility and understanding of the challenges faced by individuals leaving extremism (Schmid, 2013). Effective programmes require professionally trained staff with diverse expertise and should be part of broader support systems. In the EU, they focus on addressing factors beyond ideology, such as social and emotional support. Programmes should be tailored to individual needs, involve family and social networks, and be perceived as independent from the state for greater credibility. Long-term, consistent support is essential for success (Schmid, 2013).

De-radicalisation in cases of Islamist-motivated extremism is particularly challenging, as the ideology is deeply tied to the individual's religious beliefs. Separating faith from violent extremism and renouncing terrorism can be difficult, requiring careful intervention and guidance (Bertram, 2015).

The Aarhus de-radicalisation model offers an integrated approach to disengaging individuals associated with ISIS, combining ideological rehabilitation, psychological counselling and social reintegration (Henley, 2014). In Aarhus, Denmark, police, social services, and community leaders work together to identify and support individuals at risk of radicalisation (Henley, 2014). The Aarhus model uses mentoring, family involvement, and support in education, work, and housing to reintegrate returning jihadists. Unlike punitive approaches, it focuses on dialogue and voluntary support while monitoring risks. Though some have disengaged successfully, others remain committed, highlighting the challenges of long-term de-radicalisation. The model reflects a shift toward prevention by addressing root causes of terrorism, such as exclusion, identity struggles, and socio-economic issues (Henley, 2014).

ISIS has gained unprecedented dominance on social media and the dark web, enabling them to easily distribute propaganda. A combination of community policing and collaboration with tech companies can significantly reduce ISIS's ability to attract recruits. However, efforts to suspend ISIS-linked social media accounts have proven ineffective, mainly due to the public nature of these platforms (Gerstel, 2016). Current de-radicalisation measures have limited impact as new ISIS accounts are easily created. Suspicious accounts are mostly flagged by small hacker groups or underfunded agencies. Encouraging more users to report suspicious content on platforms like Facebook and X, could help reduce ISIS's reach. Tech companies should also use tools like PhotoDNA to automatically remove ISIS-related images, complementing community efforts without violating privacy (Gerstel, 2016).

4.5 PREVENT

PREVENT is a core part of the UK's counter-terrorism strategy, CONTEST, focused on identifying and supporting individuals vulnerable to radicalisation. It addresses all forms of terrorism, with emphasis on Extreme Right-Wing and Islamist threats, and relies on local partnerships between authorities, police, charities, and communities to deliver tailored interventions. (Home Office, 2024). In the year ending March 31, 2024, Prevent received 6,922 referrals, with age data available for 6,884 individuals. The largest proportion of referrals were for those aged 11 to 15 (2,729; 40%), followed by those aged 16 to 17 (892; 13%). For the fourth consecutive year, referrals for 'Extreme right-wing concerns' (1,314; 19%) outnumbered those for 'Islamist concerns' (913; 13%). However, this marks the first increase in Islamist-related referrals since 2019–2020 (Home Office, 2024).

The Counter-Terrorism Internet Referral Unit (CTIRU), part of the Prevent programme, tackles online radicalisation by working with tech companies to remove extremist content. Collaborating with Counter Terrorism Policing (CTP), CTIRU addresses the growing threat of extremist material, particularly on social media and encrypted platforms. Each year, around 7,000 people, mostly young individuals, are referred to Prevent. While Islamist extremism remains the primary threat, right-wing extremism is rising. CTIRU's efforts, along with support from local authorities, health services, and education, aim to prevent radicalisation before it leads to violence (CTP, 2025).

The People's Review of Prevent (PROP) report presents both successes and weaknesses of the UK's Prevent strategy. On the positive side, Prevent has been effective in early intervention, identifying individuals at risk of radicalisation. Nevertheless, the report highlights significant weaknesses, particularly in its impact on Muslim communities, with many feeling alienated by the program, leading to a lack of trust and cooperation. Additionally, there are concerns about over-referrals, where individuals who may not be at risk of radicalisation are included, diverting resources from those who truly need support (Holmwood and Aitlhadj, 2022). Widespread scepticism and concerns over civil liberties have led to calls for reform, with experts deeming it a "toxic brand" that undermines cooperation between authorities and local communities (Barcena, Daines and Noh, 2015).

4.6 CHANNEL

CHANNEL is a voluntary, confidential programme that helps people at risk of being drawn into terrorism. A panel led by the local authority, including police, health, and other partners, assesses each case and offers tailored support if appropriate. Support can include mentoring and mental health care and if radicalisation is not the issue, the person may be referred to other safeguarding services. Participation in Channel does not affect a person's criminal record or future itself (Metropolitan Police, 2025). Channel has received a more positive response than its parent programme. Since the introduction of the statutory Prevent duty in 2015, Channel has helped 5,000 individuals move away from terrorism (Metropolitan Police, 2025). The programme's success is attributed to its individualized approach, where each participant receives a tailored intervention to address their specific radicalisation factors. One-on-one mentoring and cross-agency coordination further enhance its impact. However, while Channel was initially designed for early intervention, it lacks the resources to effectively manage the growing challenge of returning fighters and already-radicalised individuals. Referrals have surged, with 1,281 cases between 2013 and 2014, many linked to rising ISIS-related investigations. Despite its promise, Channel's expansion has not been met with adequate funding, limiting its full potential in combating radicalisation (Barcena, Daines and Noh, 2015).

Overall, de-radicalisation programmes success depends on overcoming challenges like societal stigma, resource constraints, and design limitations. Long-term sustainability, ongoing support, community engagement, and continuous evaluation are very important (Saha, 2024). It is essential to focus on increasing participants' sense of belonging and strengthening their social connections within the wider community. Programmes must be carefully structured to meet these needs, supported by rigorous evaluation practices to ensure effectiveness and continuous improvement (Charkawi, Dunn and Bliuc, 2024).

Chapter 5: Conclusion

Radicalisation today is a hybrid phenomenon, with online and offline factors closely interconnected and mutually reinforcing. Some scholars agree that emphasis on the Internet's role may have overshadowed the significance of offline factors and the interaction between online and offline radicalisation (CREST, 2023). While the internet amplifies access to extremist content, it is often real-world experiences, such as a deep sense of alienation, perceived injustice, or humiliation, often intensified by social marginalisation, xenophobia, discrimination, lack of educational or employment opportunities, criminal backgrounds, or mental health issues that accelerate radicalisation (European Commission, 2016).

Through a multi-theoretical lens, primarily General Strain Theory and Social Identity Theory, it has been demonstrated that online radicalisation cannot be viewed in isolation from broader psychological and sociological factors (Borum, 2011). Radicalisation is best understood as a gradual, complex process influenced by multiple psychological and social factors, rather than a single decision or uniform pathway. Research shows there is no one-size-fits-all theory, as individuals and groups follow diverse trajectories (Borum, 2011).

The detailed study about ISIS has shown that they have effectively leveraged mainstream platforms, encrypted apps, and the dark web to create decentralised, self-directed networks that bypass traditional physical gathering points, offering isolated individuals a sense of belonging and purpose through extremist narratives (Heck, 2017).

The analysis of de-radicalisation programmes, such as Prevent and Channel, has highlighted valuable strategies, including early intervention and multi-agency collaboration. However, significant limitations persist especially talking about Prevent: it has been criticised for encouraging over-surveillance, particularly of Muslim communities, leading to wrongful referrals and fostering mistrust. Its broad scope in schools risks self-censorship among students and weakens teacher-pupil relationships. Critics argue it institutionalises Islamophobia and creates a climate of fear rather than fostering genuine safeguarding (EARS, 2021).

The progressing nature of the internet continues to shape terrorist activity, with emerging technologies like virtual reality and 3D-printed weapons creating new opportunities for radicalisation and attacks. As

these tools become more accessible, they may significantly deepen the power of online extremists (Binder and Kenyon, 2022).

Furthermore, the difficulty in accessing primary data from encrypted and dark web platforms, combined with the constantly shifting digital landscape, limits the ability of researchers and policymakers to fully grasp the mechanics of online radicalisation. Ethical constraints surrounding surveillance and data collection, add another layer of complexity (Whittaker, 2022). New online counter-terrorism efforts should place greater emphasis on reaching women, as well as younger users, recognising that radicalisation research has often focused primarily on men despite growing online involvement among women. Nevertheless, online radicalisation often affects socially isolated individuals with mental health needs, so interventions should address their broader vulnerabilities, including social support and specialist care (Kenyon, Binder and Baker-Beall, 2021). Extremist groups prioritise recruiting youth due to its strategic value, yet counter-extremism efforts fall back behind. To break the cycle of terrorism, youth radicalisation must be addressed as a core element of global security policy (IEP, 2025). At the core of long-term efforts to reduce demand for online radical propaganda is the promotion of media literacy, especially among youth. Governments should support national and local training programmes that not only teach media literacy but also help communities build the capacity to promote it. A key focus is educating internet users to identify signs of manipulative, deceptive, or misleading content (Crocì, 2024).

Key suggestion for preventing radicalisation on the internet is to directly or indirectly challenge radical ideas. Analysing firsthand accounts can help us understand how online use shape attitudes and behaviours, particularly during periods of isolation such as the COVID-19 lockdowns (CREST, 2023). Researchers agree that reducing the demand for extremist content is among the most effective ways to weaken online radical groups (Crocì, 2024).

Addressing the threats of the dark web, social media and online extremism demands a strategic blend of technological innovation, cross-border collaboration, and, most importantly, community resilience. Researchers agree that through shared intelligence and informed public engagement, society can strengthen its collective ability to protect most vulnerable from being radicalised (Al Hosani, 2024).

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